

Synthesis of α - and γ -pyrone Derivatives from 2,6-Dihydroxynaphthalene

A. P. KURIAKOSE & SURESH SETHNA

Department of Chemistry, M. S. University of Baroda, Baroda-2

6-Hydroxynaphtho(2,1; 6', 5') α -pyrone and its 4'-methyl derivative have been obtained by the Pechmann condensation of 2,6-dihydroxynaphthalene with malic acid and ethyl acetoacetate respectively. The former α -pyrone derivative on formylation and subsequent Perkin acetylation afforded naphtho(2,1 : 6',5' and 6,5 : 6',5') di- α -pyrone, the same as obtained by the Perkin acetylation of 1,5-diformyl-2,6-dihydroxynaphthalene. 1-Formyl-2,6-dihydroxynaphthalene on condensation with diethyl malonate afforded ethyl-6-hydroxynaphtho(2,1 : 6',5') α -pyrone-3'-carboxylate which on formylation and subsequent condensation with diethyl malonate gave diethyl naphtho(2,1 : 6',5' and 6,5 : 6'',5'') di- α -pyrone-3',3''-dicarboxylate, the same as obtained by the condensation of 1,5-diformyl-2,6-dihydroxynaphthalene with diethyl malonate. 1,5-Diacetyl-2,6-dihydroxynaphthalene on K.R. acetylation and benzylation afforded 3',3''-diacetyl-2',2''-dimethyl-, and 3',3''-dibenzoyl-2',2''-diphenyl-naphtho-(2,1 : 6',5' and 6,5 : 6'',5'') di- γ -pyrone respectively. The former γ -pyrone derivative was deacetylated with con. sulphuric acid but the latter could not be debenzoylated.

While a number of α - and γ -pyrone derivatives have been synthesised from α - and β -naphthol or their derivatives there appears to be only one reference in the literature on the synthesis of such derivatives from dihydroxynaphthalenes. It is the synthesis of 5-hydroxynaphthol(1,2; 6',5')- α -pyrone by the Pechmann condensation of 1,5-dihydroxynaphthalene with ethyl acetoacetate¹. It was therefore thought of interest to study the synthesis of various α - and γ -pyrone derivatives from 2,6-dihydroxynaphthalene or its appropriate derivatives.

2,6-Dihydroxynaphthalene on Pechmann condensation with malic acid gave a product which has been assigned the 6-hydroxynaphtho(2,1; 6',5')- α -pyrone structure (I) as it gave on formylation and subsequent Perkin reaction a product which was identical with the one obtained on Perkin acetylation of the known 1,5-diformyl-2,6-dihydroxynaphthalene. The Perkin acetylation product has been assigned naphtho(2,1; 6'5' and 6,5; 6'',5'') di- α -pyrone structure (IIa).

The same dihydroxynaphthalene on condensation with ethyl acetoacetate in the presence of 80% sulphuric acid gave a product in good yield which was soluble in alkali. This product on heating with alkali and dimethyl sulphate gave an unsaturated acid which is a diagnostic test for an α -pyrone derivative². The condensation is presumed to take place in 1-position in analogy with the malic acid condensation and in view of the formation of 4'-methyl naphtho(2,1; 6',5')- α -pyrone on the condensation of β -naphthol with ethyl acetoacetate³. The condensation product has therefore been assigned the 6-hydroxy-4'-methyl-naphtho(2,1; 6'5')- α -pyrone structure and the unsaturated acid has been assigned the β -methyl β ,1 (2,6-dimethoxynaphthyl)acrylic acid structure.

1-Formyl-2,6-dihydroxynaphthalene, prepared according to Gattermann⁴, on Knoevenagel condensation with diethyl malonate in the presence of piperidine gave a product to which ethyl 6-hydroxynaphtho(2,1; 6',5')- α -pyrone 3'-carboxylate structure has been assigned. This product on treatment with either cold or hot alkali did not give the corresponding acid but a product which did not melt. Dey and Lakshminarayan⁵ have observed that when naphtho α -pyrone derivatives are treated with alkali the pyrone ring may get ruptured completely. The above ester was formylated with hexamine in acetic acid but as the yield was poor the formyl derivative was prepared in a better yield through the Mannich base, prepared by reacting the ester with paraformaldehyde and dimethylamine. The Mannich base was reacted with hexamine in acetic acid and then heated with hydrochloric acid. That this was 5-formyl derivative was shown by the fact that on Knoevenagel reaction with diethyl malonate it gave the same di- α -pyrone derivative as obtained by the Knoevenagel condensation of 1,5-diformyl-2,6-dihydroxynaphthalene with diethyl malonate. The di- α -pyrone derivative is assigned the diethylnaphtho(2,1; 6',5' and 6,5: 6'',5'') di- α -pyrone-3',3''-dicarboxylate structure (IIb).

1,5-Diacetyl-2,6-dihydroxynaphthalene, prepared according to Fieser and Lothrop⁶, on Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation gave a product which analysed for the diacetyl derivative (IIIa) of the desired 2',2''-dimethylnaphtho (2,1; 6',5' and 6,5; 6'',5'') di- γ -pyrone. The acetyl groups could not be removed by treatment with alcoholic potassium hydroxide but they could be removed by treatment with con. sulphuric acid when (IIIb) was obtained.

1,5-Diacetyl-2,6-dihydroxynaphthalene on Kostanecki-Robinson benzylation with sodium benzoate and benzoic anhydride gave a product to which the 3',3''-dibenzoyl-2',2''-diphenylnaphtho(2,1; 6',5' and 6,5; 6'',5'') di γ -pyrone structure has been assigned on the basis of its analysis. It remained unchanged on treatment with hot alcoholic alkali and also with sulphuric acid. Bhuliar and Venkataraman⁷ have also noted that 3'-acylated naphtho- γ -pyrones are either unaffected or the pyrone ring was ruptured on prolonged boiling with alkali.

EXPERIMENTAL

6-Hydroxynaphtho(2,1; 6',5') α -pyrone: To a mixture of 2,6-dihydroxynaphthalene (1 g.) and malic acid (1 g.), sulphuric acid (80%; 15 ml.) was added slowly and the reaction mixture was heated in an oil bath at 120° till the effervescence ceased. It was then poured on ice and the product which separated crystallised from diphenyl ether, m. p. 260° (decomp.) (Found: C, 73.21; H, 3.76; C₁₃H₈O₃ requires, C, 73.58; H, 3.77%).

6-Hydroxy-5-formylnaphtho(2,1; 6',5') α -pyrone: 6-Hydroxynaphtho(2,1; 6',5') α -pyrone (1.5 g.) was refluxed with hexamethylene tetramine (4 g.) in glacial acetic acid gently on a wire gauge for 3/4 hr. Hydrochloric acid (1:1; 5 ml) was then added and the heating continued for further 10 minutes. After cooling, the reaction mixture was poured in cold water and the yellow solid which separated crystallised from diphenyl ether, m. p. 272°. (Found: C, 70.47; H, 3.63. C₁₄H₈O₄ requires C, 70.00; H, 3.33%)

Naphtho(2,1; 6',5' and 6,5; 6'',5'') di- α -pyrone: (a) A mixture of 6-hydroxy-5-formylnaphtho(2,1; 6',5') α -pyrone (1 g.), acetic anhydride (1.5 ml.) and freshly fused sodium acetate

(0.8 g.) was refluxed in an oil bath at 170°–80° for 8 hr. The reaction mixture was then poured on ice and the solid obtained was repeatedly crystallised from diphenyl ether, m.p. 265° (decomp.). (Found : C, 72.51; H, 3.44. $C_{16}H_3O_4$ requires C, 72.72, H, 3.03%).

(b) 1,5-Diformyl-2,6-dihydroxynaphthalene (1 g.) was mixed with acetic anhydride (1.5 ml.) and fused sodium acetate (1.2 g.) and the reaction mixture was refluxed in an oil bath at 170°–80° for 8 hr. It was poured on ice and the product which separated crystallised from diphenyl ether, m.p. 265°. Mixed m.p. with naphtho(2,1; 6',5' and 6,5: 6'',5'') di- α -pyrone described above was not depressed.

6-Hydroxy-4'-methylnaphtho(2,1; 6',5') α -pyrone : To a mixture of 2,6-dihydroxynaphthalene (1.3 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (1.3 g.), sulphuric acid (80%; 20 ml) was added gradually with shaking and external cooling. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 24 hr. and then poured on ice. The separated solid was repeatedly crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 278°. (Found : C, 74.31; H, 4.79. $C_{14}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 74.33; H, 4.43%). The product was soluble in dil. alkali and gave fluorescence with sulphuric acid

β -Methyl- β 1-(2,6-dimethoxynaphthyl) acrylic acid : 6-Hydroxy-4'-methylnaphtho (2,1; 6',5') α -pyrone (1 g.) was dissolved in a boiling mixture of acetone (50 ml) and sodium hydroxide (4%; 20 ml.) and to this solution dimethyl sulphate (2 ml.) was added slowly with continuous shaking. More of alkali and dimethyl sulphate were added with shaking and finally the mixture was heated on a steam bath for a few minutes after making it distinctly alkaline. The product obtained on acidification with dil. hydrochloric acid crystallised from dil. alcohol in reddish brown plates. The product was found to decolourise bromine water and dil. potassium permanganate solution, m.p. 206°. Yield 0.7 g. (Found : C, 70.38; H, 6.27. $C_{16}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 70.58; H, 5.88%).

Ethyl-6-hydroxynaphtho(2,1; 6',5') α -pyrone-3-carboxylate : A mixture of 1-formyl-2,6-dihydroxynaphthalene (1 g.), diethyl malonate (0.8 g.) and a few drops of piperidine was kept at room temperature for 30 hr. The reaction mixture was then treated with hydrochloric acid (5 ml.; 1 : 1) and the solid which separated was crystallised from dil. acetic acid in yellow needles (0.6 g.), m.p. 217°. (Found : C, 68.02; H, 4.54. $C_{16}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 67.61, H, 4.23%).

Ethyl-6-hydroxy-5-formylnaphtho(2,1; 6',5') α -pyrone-3'-carboxylate : Ethyl-6-hydroxynaphtho(2,1; 6',5')- α -pyrone-3'-carboxylate (1 g.) was mixed with hexamethylene tetramine (3 g.) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml.) and the reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 1/2 hr. on a wire gauze. Hydrochloric acid (5 ml.; 1 : 1) was then added and heating continued for further 1/4 hr. The product separating on pouring the reaction mixture in cold water crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 253°. (Found : C, 65.28; H, 3.95. $C_{17}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 65.37; H, 3.85%).

6-Hydroxy-5-dimethylaminomethylnaphtho(2,1; 6',5') α -pyrone-3'-carboxylate : Ethyl-6-hydroxynaphtho (2,1; 6',5')- α -pyrone-3'-carboxylate (1.2 g.) was added to alcohol (5 ml.) containing 0.1 g. of potassium hydroxide in which para-formaldehyde (0.2 g.) was dissolved

by gentle warming. Dimethylamine (0.3 g.) was then added and the reaction mixture was stirred for sometime and kept overnight. The yellow product which separated was washed with alcohol and crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether, m.p. 175°. (Found : C, 66.41; H, 5.42; N, 3.81. $C_{19}H_{19}O_5N$ requires C, 66.85; H, 5.57; N, 4.12%).

The above Mannich base (0.8 g.) and hexamethylene tetramine (2.5 g.) in glacial acetic acid (16 ml.) was heated gently on a wire gauze for 1/2 hr. Hydrochloric acid (10 ml., 1 : 1) was added and heating continued for further 1/4 hr. The product which separated on dilution with water, crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 253°. Mixed m.p. with ethyl-6-hydroxy-5-formylnaphtho(2,1; 6',5') α -pyrone-3'-carboxylate mentioned above was not depressed.

Diethylnaphtho(2,1; 6',5' and 6,5; 6'',5'') di- α -pyrone-3',3''-dicarboxylate : 1,5-Diformyl-2,6-dihydroxynaphthalene (1 g.) was mixed with diethyl malonate (1.6 g.) and a few drops of piperidine were added. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 24 hr. and then treated with hydrochloric acid (1 : 1; 10 ml). The yellow solid which separated was crystallised from glacial acetic acid after washing with sodium carbonate solution, m.p. 310°. (Found : C, 64.67; H, 4.23. $C_{22}H_{16}O_8$ requires C, 64.71; H, 3.92%).

Ethyl-6-hydroxy-5-formylnaphtho(2,1; 6',5') α -pyrone-3'-carboxylate (0.5 g.) was mixed with diethyl malonate (0.4 g.) and a few drops of piperidine were added. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 24 hr. and then treated with hydrochloric acid (1 : 1; 4 ml.). The product which separated was crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 310°. Mixed m.p. with diethylnaphtho(2,1; 6',5' and 6,5; 6'',5'') di- α -pyrone-3',3''-dicarboxylate described above was not depressed.

2',2''-Dimethyl-3',3''-diacetylnaphtho(2,1; 6',5' and 6,5; 6'',5'') di- γ -pyrone : 1,5-Diacetyl-2,6-dihydroxynaphthalene (1 g.) was heated with freshly fused and powdered sodium acetate (3.5 g.) and acetic anhydride (8 ml.) in an oil bath at 180°-90° for 10 hr. The reaction mixture was then poured in water and the solid which separated crystallised from diphenyl ether, m.p. > 350°. (Found : C, 70.12; H, 4.30; $C_{22}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 70.21; H, 4.23%).

2',2''-Dimethylnaphtho(2,1; 6',5' and 6,5; 6'',5'') di- γ -pyrone : 2',2''-Dimethyl-3',3''-diacetylnaphtho(2,1; 6',5' and 6,5; 6'',5'') di- γ -pyrone (0.5 g.) was heated gently on a wire gauze with 70% sulphuric acid (5 ml.) for 1½ hr. The reaction mixture was poured on ice and the solid which separated crystallised from acetic acid m.p. > 350°. (Found : C, 73.72; H, 3.93. $C_{19}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 73.98; H, 4.11%).

2',2''-Diphenyl-3',3''-dibenzoylnaphtho(2,1; 6',5'- and 6,5; 6'',5'') di- γ -pyrone : An intimate mixture of 1,5-diacetyl-2,6-dihydroxynaphthalene (1 g.), freshly fused sodium benzoate (2.5 g.) and benzoic anhydride (7 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 180°-90° for 10 hr. The reaction mixture was then treated repeatedly with hot water to remove sodium benzoate and benzoic anhydride and finally washed with sodium bicarbonate solution. The residue crystallised from diphenyl ether, m.p. > 350°. (Found : C, 80.67; H, 3.69. $C_{42}H_{24}O_6$ requires C, 80.76; H, 3.85%).

REFERENCES

1. R. Robinson and F. Weygand, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 386.
2. F. W. Canter and A. Robertson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1875.
3. H. V. Pechmann and J. B. Cohen, *Ber.*, 1884, **17**, 801.
4. L. Gattermann, *Annalen.*, 1907, **357**, 313, 341.
5. B. B. Dey and A. K. Lakshminarayan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **11**, 373.
6. L. F. Fieser and W. C. Lothrop, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **57**, 1459.
7. A. S. Bhullar and K. Venkataraman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1165.

